

On the Perimeter of an Ellipse: A Projection-Based Derivation and Asymptotic Error Analysis

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Abstract

This paper presents an alternative derivation of the perimeter formula of an ellipse by combining projection and calculus. It offers a different perspective compared to traditional integration methods. The purpose of this paper is to illustrate the geometrical properties of ellipses. In addition, it further develops the projection method to obtain a summation approximation based on projection, with an $\mathcal{O}(x^{-4})$ convergence rate and a relative error mostly independent of the eccentricity when e is not near 1, and the leading error term is derived via asymptotic error analysis.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Motivation

The perimeter formula of an ellipse is usually derived by parametrising the ellipse, and is expressed in terms of elliptic integrals. Although this derivation is standard, it can sometimes appear sudden and may not reveal the geometry. This paper has two main parts: Deriving the integral of the formula from the basic definition of conic sections, and deriving a geometry-based approximation. This paper does not explain why the perimeter formula of an ellipse is generally not expressible in elementary functions, nor does it give a new closed-form formula. Instead, it aims to help the reader understand the perimeter of an ellipse from a fundamental geometry perspective.

The main additional contribution is the geometry-based polygonal approximation and an asymptotic analysis based on the idea of projection. It gives a summation approximation with the leading error term independent of the eccentricity. This also reveals how the method of projection contribute to the analysis and investigation of ellipses.

1.2 Representation

Ellipses are common geometric shapes observed in various phenomena in reality, such as the shadow cast by a spherical object under parallel illumination. Geometrically, the shadow of a sphere typically forms an ellipse [1, 2].

According to the basic definition of conic sections, both ellipses and circles can be obtained by intersecting a cone with a plane [3]. This geometric relationship implies that an ellipse can be considered as the result of projecting a circle onto an inclined plane. In other words, an alternative representation for ellipses can be expressed as follows:

An ellipse is the vertical projection of a circle onto an inclined plane from a horizontal plane.

This observation emphasizes a potential connection between the circumference of a circle and the perimeter of its corresponding ellipse. It suggests that exploring this relationship may provide a method for calculating the perimeter of an ellipse.

2 PROJECTION

2.1 Elaboration

Projection is central to this paper. As mentioned above, the shadow of a spherical object is usually an ellipse. For mathematical analysis, this observation is considered as an abstract geometric description:

An ellipse on a plane (referred to later as the projective plane) is formed by the vertical projection of a circle from another plane (referred to later as the standard plane) with a projection angle [4]. Before considering the projection of a circle, it is easier to start with a simple line segment. In order to investigate the projection of a line from the basic concept of calculus, a curve can be regarded as being approximated by infinitesimal line segments. Therefore, understanding the projection principles for a line segment is necessary.

2.2 Perpendicular-line projection

First, imagine the two planes. One plane is horizontal, namely the standard plane. The other is inclined at an angle α to the horizontal, namely the projective plane. Then, we have a line l which lies on the standard plane. Let S denote the line of intersection of the two planes, and let $l \perp S$. Projecting the line segment l onto the projective plane gives a segment l' . Geometrically, l' is longer than l . We now need to determine l'/l using trigonometry. In this case, the relationship between the lengths can be determined using elementary geometry.

Figure 1: The projection of a perpendicular line segment shown in a 3-D space

In Figure 1, the intersection angle between l and l' is exactly α . Therefore, the relationship can finally be written down as $l' = l \cdot \sec \alpha$.

2.3 Parallel-line projection

The previous paragraph was considering the situation when l is perpendicular to S , and it is a special situation. In order to calculate the projected length for a general line, it is necessary to also consider the case where l is parallel to S .

Intuitively, when l is parallel to S , $l = l'$. It can be explained as follows:

Let CD be the side of the standard plane and $C'D'$ be the side of the projective plane, where both of them are parallel to S . Line AB is a line on the standard plane which is also parallel to S . Line $A'B'$ is the projected line of AB . Since $CD \parallel C'D'$, $AB \parallel CD$, and $A'B' \parallel C'D'$, it follows that $AB \parallel A'B'$. Also, the vertical distances satisfy $AA' = BB'$ as $AB \parallel S$, and both $\angle BAA'$ and $\angle ABB'$ are right angles. Therefore, $ABB'A'$ is a rectangle, which tells us that $AB = A'B'$, namely $l = l'$.

2.4 Combining the formulae

As both the projections of a perpendicular line segment and a parallel line segment are found, we can now decompose a general line segment into two components: For a general line segment \mathbf{v} , it can be decomposed into two components v_{\perp} and v_{\parallel} , where $v_{\perp} \perp S$ and $v_{\parallel} \parallel S$. Let $v_{\perp E}$ and $v_{\parallel E}$ be the projected components of \mathbf{v} . In addition, let β represent the intersection angle between \mathbf{v} and S . Therefore, $v_{\parallel} = v \cos \beta$, $v_{\perp} = v \sin \beta$. Construct coordinate systems on both the standard plane and the

projective plane. The vector of the original line segment is $\mathbf{v} = v \begin{bmatrix} \cos \beta \\ \sin \beta \end{bmatrix}$. According to the results from previous content, $v_{\parallel E} = v_{\parallel}$, $v_{\perp E} = v_{\perp} \sec \alpha$. Therefore, the vector of the projected line segment is:

$$\mathbf{v}_E = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & \sec \alpha \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_{\parallel} \\ v_{\perp} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & \sec \alpha \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{v} = \mathbf{M}\mathbf{v} \quad (1)$$

Where $\mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & \sec \alpha \end{bmatrix}$ is hence the "Projection scaling matrix". This is natural, because projection can be regarded as a linear map of a vector from the standard plane to the projective plane. With further substitution, we can rewrite the formula as: $\mathbf{v}_E = v \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & \sec \alpha \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos \beta \\ \sin \beta \end{bmatrix} = v \begin{bmatrix} \cos \beta \\ \sin \beta \sec \alpha \end{bmatrix}$. Therefore, $\|\mathbf{v}_E\| = v\sqrt{\sin^2 \beta \sec^2 \alpha + \cos^2 \beta}$. This serves as another form of the matrix calculation.

3 CALCULUS-BASED DERIVATION

3.1 Differentiation and Substitution

The next step is applying Equation 1 to a circle on a standard plane. The problem here is that arcs cannot be substituted into the equation directly. Therefore, we need to differentiate the circumference and apply the formula on the infinitesimal line segments. By parametrising a circle:

$$\mathbf{r}(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} r \cos \theta \\ r \sin \theta \end{bmatrix} \quad \theta \in [0, 2\pi]$$

$$\frac{d\mathbf{r}}{d\theta} = \mathbf{t}(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{dx}{d\theta} \\ \frac{dy}{d\theta} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -r \sin \theta \\ r \cos \theta \end{bmatrix}$$

From the definition of derivatives, the tangent vector can be rewritten as:

$$\mathbf{t}(\theta) := \frac{d\mathbf{r}}{d\theta} = \lim_{\Delta\theta \rightarrow 0} \frac{\mathbf{r}(\theta + \Delta\theta) - \mathbf{r}(\theta)}{\Delta\theta}$$

The expression $\mathbf{r}(\theta + \Delta\theta) - \mathbf{r}(\theta)$ is the infinitesimal displacement on the circumference due to $\Delta\theta$. When $\Delta\theta \rightarrow 0$, we write it as $d\mathbf{r}$, which is exactly the infinitesimal line segment. Therefore, we can rearrange the equations above and apply the projection scaling matrix \mathbf{M} to the line segments.

$$d\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{t}(\theta)d\theta$$

$$\mathbf{M}d\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{M}\mathbf{t}(\theta)d\theta = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & \sec \alpha \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} -r \sin \theta \\ r \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} d\theta = \begin{bmatrix} -r \sin \theta \\ r \sec \alpha \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} d\theta$$

As we are only interested in the magnitude of the vector for obtaining the perimeter of an ellipse, we take its norm:

$$\|\mathbf{M}\mathbf{t}(\theta)\| d\theta = \left\| \begin{bmatrix} -r \sin \theta \\ r \sec \alpha \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \right\| d\theta = \sqrt{r^2 \sin^2 \theta + r^2 \sec^2 \alpha \cos^2 \theta} d\theta = r\sqrt{\sin^2 \theta + \sec^2 \alpha \cos^2 \theta} d\theta$$

Therefore, if we let $dr_E = \|d\mathbf{r}_E\| = \|\mathbf{M}\mathbf{t}(\theta)\| d\theta$ be the projected infinitesimal line segment, we can say that:

$$\|\mathbf{M}d\mathbf{r}\| = dr_E = r\sqrt{\sin^2 \theta + \sec^2 \alpha \cos^2 \theta} d\theta \quad (2)$$

3.2 Integrating the projected infinitesimal line segments

The perimeter of the ellipse on the projective plane is the projected circumference of the corresponding circle on the standard plane. In the previous section, we expressed the projected infinitesimal line segments of the circumference, the final step we need to take here is therefore integrating the projected line segments over the parameter range with Equation 2. Recall that $\theta \in [0, 2\pi]$:

$$P_{\text{ellipse}} = \int_0^{2\pi} \|\mathbf{M}\mathbf{t}(\theta)\| d\theta$$

$$P_{\text{ellipse}} = \int_0^{2\pi} r\sqrt{\sin^2 \theta + \cos^2 \theta \sec^2 \alpha} d\theta.$$

3.3 Simplification

On the projective plane, the semi-major axis a is the projection of the radius of the circle that is perpendicular to the line of intersection. The semi-minor axis b is actually equal to the radius, because it is from the projection of the radius that is parallel to the line of intersection. Therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} b &= r \\ a &= \sec(\alpha) \cdot r = \sec(\alpha) \cdot b \\ \sec(\alpha) &= \frac{a}{b} \end{aligned}$$

By substituting:

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\text{ellipse}} &= \int_0^{2\pi} b \sqrt{\cos^2 \theta \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^2 + \sin^2 \theta} d\theta \\ P_{\text{ellipse}} &= \int_0^{2\pi} \sqrt{a^2 \cos^2 \theta + b^2 \sin^2 \theta} d\theta \end{aligned}$$

Notice the symmetry property of the integrand. Let the integrand be $f(\theta)$: First, $f(\theta - \pi/2) = f(\theta + \pi/2)$, because $\cos^2(\theta + \pi/2) = \cos^2(\theta - \pi/2)$ and $\sin^2(\theta + \pi/2) = \sin^2(\theta - \pi/2)$. Second, $f(\theta + \pi) = f(\theta - \pi)$, because $\cos^2(\theta + \pi) = \cos^2(\theta - \pi)$ and $\sin^2(\theta + \pi) = \sin^2(\theta - \pi)$. Therefore, this integrand has four identical parts in the interval $\theta \in [0, 2\pi]$. This integral can be written as:

$$P_{\text{ellipse}} = 4 \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sqrt{a^2 \cos^2 \theta + b^2 \sin^2 \theta} d\theta$$

Extract a out of the square root, gives:

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\text{ellipse}} &= 4a \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sqrt{\cos^2 \theta + \frac{b^2}{a^2} \sin^2 \theta} d\theta \\ P_{\text{ellipse}} &= 4a \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sqrt{1 - \left(1 - \frac{b^2}{a^2}\right) \sin^2 \theta} d\theta \end{aligned}$$

By the definition of eccentricity, $e = \frac{c}{a} = \frac{\sqrt{a^2 - b^2}}{a} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{b^2}{a^2}} = \sqrt{1 - \cos^2 \alpha} = \sin \alpha$.

$$P_{\text{ellipse}} = 4a \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sqrt{1 - e^2 \sin^2 \theta} d\theta$$

Define $E(k) := \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sqrt{1 - k^2 \sin^2 \theta} d\theta$, which is the complete elliptic integral of the second kind [5]. Therefore:

$$P_{\text{ellipse}} = 4aE(e)$$

This is the simplest form of this equation.

4 APPROXIMATION

4.1 Another approach from the method of projection

Besides using differential arc length, another method for approximating the perimeter of an ellipse is by projecting polygon segments. When approximating a circumference, a natural first idea is to use a regular polygon with sufficiently many sides. For instance, a 120-sided regular inscribed polygon would be extremely close to a circle. In the previous sections, infinitesimal arc lengths were used to approximate the circumference, then each of them was projected. In this section, the same idea will be applied, but without directly integrating infinitesimal line segments.

Imagine an inscribed polygon in a circle. Due to the symmetry feature of a circle, it is possible to separate the circle into four identical pieces (Shown in Figure 3). For convenience, we take the number of sides of the polygon to be a multiple of four. For each side on the regular polygon, we can apply

the projection formula to approximate an ellipse. Each side has the same length, but with different intersection angles. Recall the projection formula:

$$v_E = v\sqrt{\sin^2 \beta \sec^2 \alpha + \cos^2 \beta}$$

The angle β can be determined first.

Figure 2: An inscribed octagon

Figure 2 can be used as an example. Suppose that the inscribed regular polygon has n sides, therefore each of its interior angle is $\frac{(n-2)\pi}{n} = \pi - \frac{2\pi}{n}$. We name this angle as ω first. According to Figure 2, the intersection angle for the first side would be $\beta_1 = \frac{\pi - \omega}{2}$. By alternating angles, the second intersection angle $\beta_2 = \pi - (\omega - \beta_1) = \frac{3(\pi - \omega)}{2}$. Therefore, as $\beta_k = \pi - \omega + \beta_{k-1}$, and $\beta_1 = \frac{\pi - \omega}{2}$, we can find out the pattern via mathematical induction:

$$\beta_k = \beta_1 + (k - 1)(\pi - \omega) = \frac{\pi - \omega}{2} + (k - 1)(\pi - \omega) = \frac{(2k - 1)(\pi - \omega)}{2}$$

By substituting ω by $\pi - \frac{2\pi}{n}$, the formula for the intersection angle can therefore be obtained:

$$\beta_k = \frac{(2k - 1)(\pi - \omega)}{2} = \frac{(2k - 1)\pi}{n}$$

Another component we need is the side length.

Figure 3: An arc with a chord and a tangent

Figure 3 shows the details of one sector. When approximating the arc \widehat{CB} , both line segment ED and CB are simple approximations. However, neither of them is sufficiently accurate. Therefore, a weighted average of those two line segments can be used. First, the length of those two line segments can be calculated. Let $\angle BOC = \theta$, $CO = AO = BO = r$, and we can obtain:

$$CB = 2\left(OC \sin \frac{\theta}{2}\right) = 2r \sin \frac{\theta}{2}$$

$$ED = 2\left(EA \tan \frac{\theta}{2}\right) = 2r \tan \frac{\theta}{2}$$

The determination of weight is the key step. Let ϕ be the weight assigned to CB , therefore the weighted average $A = 2\phi r \sin \frac{\theta}{2} + 2(1 - \phi)r \tan \frac{\theta}{2}$. The main difficulty lies in the trigonometric terms, therefore the Taylor series of sine and tangent functions can be introduced. We take the Taylor expansion up to the cubic term: [6]

$$2r \sin \frac{\theta}{2} = r\theta - \frac{r\theta^3}{24} + \mathcal{O}(\theta^5)$$

$$2r \tan \frac{\theta}{2} = r\theta + \frac{r\theta^3}{12} + \mathcal{O}(\theta^5)$$

Therefore:

$$A = \phi\left(r\theta - \frac{r\theta^3}{24}\right) + (1 - \phi)\left(r\theta + \frac{r\theta^3}{12}\right) \approx \widehat{CB} = r\theta$$

For the linear terms, $r\theta(\phi + 1 - \phi) \equiv r\theta$, therefore the leading error mainly comes in the cubic terms. In order to eliminate the error, the cubic term coefficient has to be 0:

$$-\frac{\phi}{24} + \frac{1 - \phi}{12} = 0$$

$$\phi = \frac{2}{3}$$

In theory, we can take higher-order Taylor series to make it more accurate. However, that will significantly complicate the calculation by introducing higher-order terms. Hence, the final length we take for the projection is $\frac{4r \sin \frac{\theta}{2} + 2r \tan \frac{\theta}{2}}{3} = \frac{4b \sin \frac{\theta}{2} + 2b \tan \frac{\theta}{2}}{3}$. It is worth mentioning that this coincides with a Huygens-type approximation for circular arc length [7, 8]: Let $u = \frac{\theta}{2}$, the Huygens-type approximation, or generally the Huygens inequality gives $\frac{4r \sin u + 2r \tan u}{3} \gtrsim 2ru$, which is exactly $A \gtrsim r\theta$, where $r\theta$ is the

actual arc length. Now, we will use the projection formula again. The projected length for one side would be:

$$\frac{4b \sin \frac{\theta}{2} + 2b \tan \frac{\theta}{2}}{3} \sqrt{\sin^2 \left(\frac{(2k-1)\pi}{n} \right) \sec^2 \alpha + \cos^2 \left(\frac{(2k-1)\pi}{n} \right)}$$

However, we need a total projected length rather than a single projected side:

$$4 \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{n}{4}} \frac{4b \sin \frac{\theta}{2} + 2b \tan \frac{\theta}{2}}{3} \sqrt{\sin^2 \left(\frac{(2k-1)\pi}{n} \right) \sec^2 \alpha + \cos^2 \left(\frac{(2k-1)\pi}{n} \right)}$$

The upper bound $\frac{n}{4}$ comes from taking only a quarter of the polygon. Therefore, a factor of 4 is needed to obtain the whole perimeter. In order to simplify the notation, let $x = \frac{n}{4}$, $n = 4x$. Here, x denotes the number of sides in one quadrant of the polygon instead of the whole polygon. We apply this to simplify the sum:

$$\frac{16b \sin \frac{\theta}{2} + 8b \tan \frac{\theta}{2}}{3} \sum_{k=1}^x \sqrt{\sin^2 \left((2k-1) \frac{\pi}{4x} \right) \sec^2 \alpha + \cos^2 \left((2k-1) \frac{\pi}{4x} \right)}$$

Recall the definition of θ , where $\theta = \frac{2\pi}{4x} = \frac{\pi}{2x}$. By further trigonometric simplification, the simplified version would be:

$$P_{\text{approx}}(x) = \frac{8b}{3} \sin \left(\frac{\pi}{4x} \right) \left(2 + \sec \left(\frac{\pi}{4x} \right) \right) \sum_{k=1}^x \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{4x} (2k-1) \right)}$$

Taking the limit as $x \rightarrow \infty$ gives the exact perimeter of an ellipse, which is:

$$P_{\text{ellipse}} = \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{8b}{3} \sin \left(\frac{\pi}{4x} \right) \left(2 + \sec \left(\frac{\pi}{4x} \right) \right) \sum_{k=1}^x \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{4x} (2k-1) \right)}$$

4.2 Numerical comparison

The table below compares the proposed approximation with Ramanujan's second approximation [9, 10] for ellipses with different eccentricities, using $b = 1$, and $x = 25, 50, 100$ respectively.

Table 1: Comparison of ellipse perimeter approximations ($b = 1$, $x = 25$)

e	Exact value	$P_{\text{approx}}(25)$	Ramanujan approx.	$P_{\text{approx}}(25)$ Rel. error	Ramanujan Rel. error
0.10	6.299022	6.299022	6.299022	4.872×10^{-8}	2.295×10^{-31}
0.20	6.348133	6.348133	6.348133	4.872×10^{-8}	2.805×10^{-25}
0.30	6.435771	6.435771	6.435771	4.872×10^{-8}	1.214×10^{-21}
0.40	6.572468	6.572468	6.572468	4.872×10^{-8}	5.646×10^{-19}
0.50	6.777918	6.777918	6.777918	4.872×10^{-8}	8.391×10^{-17}
0.60	7.090417	7.090417	7.090417	4.872×10^{-8}	6.679×10^{-15}
0.70	7.593221	7.593222	7.593221	4.872×10^{-8}	3.96×10^{-13}
0.80	8.509000	8.509000	8.509000	4.872×10^{-8}	2.387×10^{-11}
0.85	9.325351	9.325351	9.325351	4.872×10^{-8}	2.153×10^{-10}
0.90	10.752230	10.752230	10.752230	4.872×10^{-8}	2.523×10^{-9}
0.95	14.126143	14.126143	14.126142	4.872×10^{-8}	5.514×10^{-8}
0.96	15.522092	15.522093	15.522090	4.872×10^{-8}	1.207×10^{-7}
0.97	17.591524	17.591525	17.591518	4.872×10^{-8}	2.956×10^{-7}
0.98	21.107649	21.107650	21.107630	4.872×10^{-8}	8.728×10^{-7}
0.99	29.162687	29.162688	29.162576	4.936×10^{-8}	3.803×10^{-6}

Table 2: Data of P_{approx} at $x = 50$ and $x = 100$ ($b = 1$)

e	$P_{\text{approx}}(50)$	$P_{\text{approx}}(50)$ Rel. error	$P_{\text{approx}}(100)$	$P_{\text{approx}}(100)$ Rel. error
0.10	6.299022	3.044×10^{-9}	6.299022	1.903×10^{-10}
0.20	6.348133	3.044×10^{-9}	6.348133	1.903×10^{-10}
0.30	6.435771	3.044×10^{-9}	6.435771	1.903×10^{-10}
0.40	6.572468	3.044×10^{-9}	6.572468	1.903×10^{-10}
0.50	6.777918	3.044×10^{-9}	6.777918	1.903×10^{-10}
0.60	7.090417	3.044×10^{-9}	7.090417	1.903×10^{-10}
0.70	7.593221	3.044×10^{-9}	7.593221	1.903×10^{-10}
0.80	8.509000	3.044×10^{-9}	8.509000	1.903×10^{-10}
0.85	9.325351	3.044×10^{-9}	9.325351	1.903×10^{-10}
0.90	10.752230	3.044×10^{-9}	10.752230	1.903×10^{-10}
0.95	14.126143	3.044×10^{-9}	14.126143	1.903×10^{-10}
0.96	15.522092	3.044×10^{-9}	15.522092	1.903×10^{-10}
0.97	17.591524	3.044×10^{-9}	17.591524	1.903×10^{-10}
0.98	21.107649	3.044×10^{-9}	21.107649	1.903×10^{-10}
0.99	29.162687	3.044×10^{-9}	29.162687	1.903×10^{-10}

The relative error is calculated by the formula $\left| \frac{P_{\text{approx}}(x) - P_{\text{exact}}}{P_{\text{exact}}} \right|$.

Two features stand out from these tables. First, the relative error of the proposed approximation is nearly independent of the eccentricity: for a certain x , the relative error remains almost constant across the entire range from $e = 0.10$ to $e = 0.99$. This is in contrast to Ramanujan's second approximation, whose relative error grows by more than twenty five orders of magnitude as e increases from 0.10 to 0.99. Also, we discover that doubling x reduces the relative error by approximately a factor of 16, suggesting an $\mathcal{O}(x^{-4})$ convergence rate. This rate originates from the weighted average approximation previously, whose error is $\mathcal{O}(\theta^5)$ for each segment. However, in Table 1, the relative error of $P_{\text{approx}}(25)$ at $e = 0.99$ shows a different numerical result compared to other data in the table. This potentially shows that the relative error might still depend on the eccentricity.

The two methods cross at an eccentricity e^* , which depends on x : Numerically, e^* around 0.95 for $x = 25$, e^* around 0.9 for $x = 50$, and e^* around 0.85 for $x = 100$. Below e^* , Ramanujan's second approximation is more accurate, attaining relative errors of 10^{-31} at $e = 0.10$ where the proposed approximation gives only 10^{-8} at $x = 25$. Above e^* , the proposed summation is more accurate, where it is more accurate by more than two orders of magnitude near $e = 0.99$ at $x = 25$. Since e^* decreases as x grows, the proposed approximation exceeds Ramanujan's second approximation over a progressively wider range of eccentricities as x is increased, though the transition may be slow.

Since both $P_{\text{approx}}(x)$ and P_{exact} have a factor of b , it cancels out in the fraction of the relative error. Therefore, the relative error is absolutely independent of b . This will be further proved in Section 4.3. We can hypothesize that the relative error mostly depends on the value of x . We can plot a log-log graph when x varies:

Figure 4: Log-log plot of relative error against x

From Figure 4, when x is small, the line bends down a little bit. When x increases, it becomes approximately linear. This indicates a potential power law relationship $E_{rel} \approx Cx^{-4}$ which is observed from the figure. This also supports the $\mathcal{O}(x^{-4})$ convergence rate. From the plotting, $C \approx 0.019$. This will be further discussed in Section 4.3, too.

4.3 Asymptotic error analysis

To prove the hypothesis from the previous section, we need to find out where the error comes from. In Section 4.1, we omitted the $\mathcal{O}(\theta^5)$ terms in the Taylor expansion. For the factor $\frac{4b \sin \frac{\theta}{2} + 2b \tan \frac{\theta}{2}}{3}$ we used, it implies that the main error may come from the $\mathcal{O}(\theta^5)$. With further Taylor expansion:

$$A = \frac{4b \sin \frac{\theta}{2} + 2b \tan \frac{\theta}{2}}{3} = b\theta + 0 + \frac{b\theta^5}{320} + \dots$$

The θ^3 term becomes 0, which is what we expected with the weighted average. Recall the Huygens inequality $A > r\theta$, for each segment of the polygon, the error is:

$$A - r\theta = \frac{b\theta^5}{320} + \mathcal{O}(\theta^7)$$

This error also experiences the projection while the whole polygon is projected. This can be expressed as:

$$(A - r\theta)\sqrt{\sin^2 \beta \sec^2 \alpha + \cos^2 \beta} = (A - r\theta)\sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 \beta}$$

This is the error after projection for one single segment with a certain β . However, the total absolute error is more complicated. In order to calculate the total absolute error, we need a summation. Let E_{abs} denote the total absolute error. Intuitively, the error must be related to the expression $(A - r\theta)\sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 \beta}$.

$$E_{abs}(x) = P_{approx}(x) - P_{exact} = 4A \sum_{k=1}^x \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 \beta_k} - 4 \int_0^{\pi/2} \|\mathbf{Mt}(\theta)\| d\theta$$

In order to complete a term with the factor $(A - r\theta)$:

$$E_{abs}(x) = 4A \sum_{k=1}^x \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 \beta_k} - 4r\theta \sum_{k=1}^x \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 \beta_k} + 4r\theta \sum_{k=1}^x \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 \beta_k} - 4 \int_0^{\pi/2} \|\mathbf{Mt}(\theta)\| d\theta$$

$$E_{\text{abs}}(x) = 4(A - r\theta) \sum_{k=1}^x \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 \beta_k} + \left(4r\theta \sum_{k=1}^x \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 \beta_k} - 4 \int_0^{\pi/2} \|\mathbf{Mt}(\theta)\| d\theta \right)$$

Where $\beta_k = \frac{(2k-1)\pi}{n}$ from Section 4.1. Here, we can see a part similar to the expression $(A-r\theta)\sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 \beta}$, which is the error caused by the weighted average A ; We call it $E_{\text{app}}(x)$. The second part is the discretisation error, which occurs when we are using a finite summation to approach an integral; We call it $E_{\text{mid}}(x)$. We are going to work with $E_{\text{mid}}(x)$ first, and prove that it is mostly negligible to the entire error $E_{\text{abs}}(x)$. According to the Euler-Maclaurin formula to the midpoint rule discrepancy [11]:

$$E_{\text{mid}}(x) = 4r \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{B_{2j}(1/2)}{(2j)!} h^{2j} \left(f^{(2j-1)}\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) - f^{(2j-1)}(0) \right) + R_m(x), \quad m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$$

Where $R_m(x)$ is the remainder. For the function $f(\beta) = \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 \beta}$, we are going to prove that for any of its odd-order derivatives, $(f^{(2j-1)}(\frac{\pi}{2}) - f^{(2j-1)}(0)) = 0$.

When $\beta = 0$: Because $\sin^2(\beta)$ is an even function, $f(\beta)$ is also an even function. The odd-order derivative of an even function must be an odd function. An odd function must pass through the origin. Therefore: $f^{(2j-1)}(0) = 0$.

When $\beta = \pi/2$: Let $g(x) = f(x + \pi/2) = f(\beta) = \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \cos^2 x}$, so $\beta = x + \pi/2$. As $\cos^2(x)$ is an even function, $g(x)$ is also an even function. As mentioned before, $g^{(2j-1)}(x)$ must be an odd function, and it must pass through the origin, which means: $g^{(2j-1)}(0) = 0$. As $g(x) = f(x + \pi/2)$, $g(0) = f(\pi/2)$, $f^{(2j-1)}(\pi/2) = g^{(2j-1)}(0) = 0$.

Therefore, $(f^{(2j-1)}(\frac{\pi}{2}) - f^{(2j-1)}(0)) = 0 - 0 = 0$, $E_{\text{mid}}(x) = R_m(x)$, which means all algebraic endpoint correction terms in the Euler-Maclaurin expansion disappear. As f is an analytic periodic function, the midpoint rule has exponentially small discretisation error. This means that $E_{\text{mid}}(x)$ decays exponentially [12, 13]. As $\mathcal{O}(\exp(-\delta x)) \ll \mathcal{O}(x^{-N})$, this allows it to be included in later $\mathcal{O}(x^{-6})$. Specifically, according to the Trefethen-Weideman analysis [12], E_{mid} decays exponentially by $\exp(-\frac{2\pi\delta}{\Delta t})$, where Δt for this periodic function f is $\Delta t = \frac{2\pi}{4x} = \frac{\pi}{2x}$. Therefore, $E_{\text{mid}} = \mathcal{O}_e(\exp(-4x\delta))$, where $\mathcal{O}_e(\dots)$ indicates a big- \mathcal{O} notation whose implicit constant may depend on a fixed e , but not on x . In later paragraphs, we will discuss why $\mathcal{O}_e(\exp(-4x\delta))$ is related to the eccentricity.

Now, we can move on to the $E_{\text{app}}(x)$. We can use the midpoint rule here to evaluate the summation by an integral:

$$\sum_{k=1}^x f(\beta_k) \cdot \Delta t \approx \int_0^{\pi/2} f(\beta) d\beta$$

Where $\Delta t = \frac{\pi/2}{x} = \frac{\pi}{2x}$ as we are separating a quadrant into x parts. Therefore:

$$\frac{\pi}{2x} \sum_{k=1}^x \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 \beta_k} \approx \int_0^{\pi/2} \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 t} dt$$

The discretisation error due to the midpoint rule is what we derived previously, $\mathcal{O}_e(\exp(-4\delta x))$. Therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\pi}{2x} \sum_{k=1}^x \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 \beta_k} &\approx \int_0^{\pi/2} \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 t} dt + \mathcal{O}_e(\exp(-4\delta x)) \\ \sum_{k=1}^x \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 \beta_k} &\approx \frac{2x}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi/2} \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 t} dt + \mathcal{O}_e(x \exp(-4\delta x)) \end{aligned}$$

This integral can be simplified further:

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_0^{\pi/2} \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 t} dt \\ &= \int_0^{\pi/2} \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha - \tan^2 \alpha \cos^2 t} dt \\ &= \int_0^{\pi/2} \sqrt{\sec^2 \alpha - \tan^2 \alpha \cos^2 t} dt \end{aligned}$$

Let $u = \frac{\pi}{2} - t$, $du = d(-t)$. Recall the complete elliptic integral of the second kind $E(k)$:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sec \alpha \int_{\pi/2}^0 \sqrt{1 - e^2 \sin^2 u} (-du) \\ &= \frac{a}{b} \int_0^{\pi/2} \sqrt{1 - e^2 \sin^2 u} du \\ &= \frac{a}{b} E(e) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore:

$$\sum_{k=1}^x \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 \beta_k} \approx \frac{2axE(e)}{b\pi} + \mathcal{O}_e(x \exp(-4\delta x))$$

$$E_{\text{abs}}(x) = E_{\text{app}}(x) + E_{\text{mid}}(x) = 4(A - r\theta) \left(\frac{2axE(e)}{b\pi} + \mathcal{O}_e(x \exp(-4\delta x)) \right) + \mathcal{O}_e(\exp(-4\delta x))$$

Recall the central angle θ from Section 4.1. As we are separating the polygon into $4x$ parts, the central angle θ for each segment would be $\theta = \frac{2\pi}{4x} = \frac{\pi}{2x}$. Also, recall that $A - r\theta = \frac{b\theta^5}{320} + \mathcal{O}(\theta^7) = \frac{\pi^5 b}{10240x^5} + \mathcal{O}(x^{-7})$:

$$E_{\text{abs}}(x) = 4 \left(\frac{\pi^5 b}{10240x^5} + \mathcal{O}(x^{-7}) \right) \left(\frac{2axE(e)}{b\pi} + \mathcal{O}_e(x \exp(-4\delta x)) \right) + \mathcal{O}_e(\exp(-4\delta x))$$

By expanding the brackets:

$$E_{\text{abs}}(x) = \frac{\pi^4 a E(e)}{1280x^4} + \frac{8axE(e)}{b\pi} \mathcal{O}(x^{-7}) + \frac{\pi^5 b}{10240x^5} \mathcal{O}_e(x \exp(-4\delta x)) + \mathcal{O}(x^{-7}) \mathcal{O}_e(x \exp(-4\delta x)) + \mathcal{O}_e(\exp(-4\delta x))$$

$$E_{\text{abs}}(x) = \frac{\pi^4 a E(e)}{1280x^4} + \mathcal{O}_e(x^{-6}) + \mathcal{O}_e(x^{-4} \exp(-4\delta x)) + \mathcal{O}_e(x^{-6} \exp(-4\delta x)) + \mathcal{O}_e(\exp(-4\delta x))$$

All the other higher-order terms are absorbed by the largest remainder $\mathcal{O}_e(x^{-6})$.

$$E_{\text{abs}}(x) = \frac{\pi^4 a E(e)}{1280x^4} + \mathcal{O}_e(x^{-6})$$

As the exact perimeter of an ellipse is $P_{\text{exact}} = 4aE(e)$:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\text{rel}}(x) &= \frac{E_{\text{abs}}(x)}{P_{\text{exact}}} \\ E_{\text{rel}}(x) &= \frac{\pi^4}{5120x^4} + \mathcal{O}_e(x^{-6}) \quad e \in (0, 1) \\ E_{\text{rel}}(x) &\approx \frac{\pi^4}{5120x^4} \end{aligned}$$

Where $\pi^4/5120 \approx 0.0190252$, matches the observed coefficient C and the exponent -4 from Figure 4 at the end of Section 4.2 ($E_{\text{rel}}(x) \approx 0.019x^{-4}$). Also, this can prove that the relative error is independent of b , as b is cancelled out in the expression of E_{rel} . This can be numerically verified: For $P_{\text{approx}}(25)$, the relative error should approximately be $\frac{\pi^4}{5120 \cdot 25^4} = \frac{\pi^4}{5120 \times 390625} \approx 4.872 \times 10^{-8}$, which matches the data in Table 1. Also, there is an exception in Table 1, which is when $e = 0.99$. The leading term in the error $\frac{\pi^4}{5120x^4}$ is not affected by the eccentricity, but the $\mathcal{O}_e(x^{-6})$ does as there are terms associated with the eccentricity in the $\mathcal{O}(x^{-6})$. When the eccentricity becomes too large, the $\mathcal{O}(x^{-6})$ becomes non-negligible.

This discrepancy also has a practical use. Let ϵ denote the discrepancy, so that $\epsilon \approx \frac{\pi^4}{5120x^4}$. Making x the subject gives $x \approx (\frac{\pi^4}{5120\epsilon})^{1/4}$. This tells us how many segments x are needed to achieve a certain accuracy. For example, for an accuracy of $\epsilon = 10^{-6}$, we need an $x \approx 12$ for most values of $e \in (0, 1)$.

In addition, the constant δ can be solved. According to the exponential convergence principle for analytic periodic functions, the discretisation error of the midpoint rule decays exponentially with a decay rate determined by the distance from the real axis to the nearest singularity of the integrand in the complex plane [14, 15]. Consider extending the function $f(z) = \sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 z}$ into the complex plane. For $f(z)$ to have a singularity, the radicand should be zero, which is $1 + \tan^2 \alpha \sin^2 z = 0$. This equation yields a result of $z = n\pi \pm i \sinh^{-1}(\cot \alpha)$. The distance from the singularity to the real axis is therefore $\delta = \sinh^{-1}(\cot \alpha)$. Therefore, $E_{\text{mid}}(x) = \mathcal{O}_e(\exp(-4 \sinh^{-1}(\cot \alpha)x))$, where

$\cot \alpha = \frac{\sqrt{1-\sin^2 \alpha}}{\sin \alpha} = \frac{\sqrt{1-e^2}}{e}$. When $e \rightarrow 1$, $\cot \alpha \rightarrow 0$, and $\sinh^{-1}(\cot \alpha) \rightarrow 0$, which leads to larger $\exp(-4 \sinh^{-1}(\cot \alpha)x)$, so the error decays more slowly. This explains why a large eccentricity near one triggers the non-negligible $\mathcal{O}_e(x^{-6})$ remainder, which becomes more visible in the total relative error when e gets closer to one.

5 CONCLUSION

In summary, this paper proposed a projection scaling matrix \mathbf{M} for projection, and the final result obtained from projection and calculus is equivalent to the result obtained from traditional integrals. This derivation results in the standard elliptic integral as shown. The approach, originating from the geometric definition of the ellipse as a projection, supports the idea that the perimeter of an ellipse is not generally expressible in elementary functions [5]. In addition, this paper provides a projection-based summation approximation of the perimeter of an ellipse. The numerical comparison suggests that the relative error of the proposed approximation is nearly independent of the eccentricity, and it can be more accurate than Ramanujan's second approximation when the eccentricity is large, with an $\mathcal{O}(x^{-4})$ convergence rate. Also, the approximation is supported by a mathematical proof, reinforces its convergence rate and leading nearly eccentricity-independent relative error term, and provides space for future development.

Declaration of Generative AI Support

AI tools, including ChatGPT by OpenAI, Claude by Anthropic, and Gemini by Google, were used as auxiliary aids during the preparation of this paper. These tools assisted with the Python code in Section 4.2 for plotting and numerical computations. The background ideas in Section 4.3 related to real analysis and complex analysis were studied and discussed with the assistance of AI tools. No final text was generated by AI tools; all final text was written by the author after independently understanding the ideas and reviewing the grammar and terminology suggestions given by AI tools. All suggestions given by these tools were strictly checked, discussed, and verified by the author; AI tools were not used as authors. All formulae, mathematical computations, citations, and claims were produced, performed, selected, or verified by the author, who takes full responsibility for the integrity and accuracy of the content of the paper.

Appendix: Notations

Symbol	Meaning (geometric interpretation)
a	major semi-axis of the ellipse
b	minor semi-axis of the ellipse
c	focal distance of the ellipse
e	eccentricity of the ellipse, where $e = \sin \alpha = \frac{c}{a}$
r	radius of the generating circle (often $r = b$ in this setup)
α	inclination angle between the two planes (projection angle), where $b \cdot \sec \alpha = a$
θ	parameter angle on the circle/ellipse (as defined in the derivation)
β	the intersection angle between \mathbf{v} and S
S	line of intersection of the two planes
\mathbf{M}	projection scaling matrix, where $\mathbf{M} = \text{diag}(1, \sec \alpha)$
P_{ellipse}	perimeter of the ellipse
P_{exact}	exact value of the perimeter of the ellipse
P_{approx}	approximate perimeter of the ellipse
\mathbf{v}	vector of line segment before projection
\mathbf{v}_E	vector of line segment after projection
v	length of \mathbf{v} ($v = \ \mathbf{v}\ $)
v_E	length of \mathbf{v}_E ($v_E = \ \mathbf{v}_E\ $)
$d\mathbf{r}$	vector of infinitesimal line element before projection
$d\mathbf{r}_E$	vector of infinitesimal line element after projection
E_{abs}	absolute error ($E_{\text{abs}} = E_{\text{app}} + E_{\text{mid}}$)
E_{app}	error due to the polygonal approximation
E_{mid}	error due to the midpoint rule
E_{rel}	relative error ($E_{\text{rel}} = \frac{E_{\text{abs}}}{P_{\text{exact}}}$)
ϵ	discrepancy of the proposed approximation
δ	half-width of the strip of analyticity; distance from the closest singularity to the real axis
$\mathcal{O}_e(\dots)$	Big- \mathcal{O} notation whose implicit constant may depend on a fixed e , but not on x

Table 3: Notation used throughout the paper.

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